

**THE INVESTMENT AND THE IMPACT IN INNOVATIVE LOGISTICS:
AN ECONOMIC GROWTH**

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to the role and development of investment for the supply chain as an innovative solution. The study examines the stakeholder's active participation in the process of investment. The characteristics and trends in the process of investment are examined. Companies are increasingly investing in digital technologies, automation, and artificial intelligence to streamline their operations, reduce costs, and enhance customer experience. The trend of dynamic innovations of investment in the supply chain management and logistics industries in the world represents a significant opportunity for economic growth and development. The result shows with an increase in the investment and transport industry, more companies are participating in the supply chain globally. The increasing investment trend also highlights the importance of supply chain management and logistics in today's global economy and the recognition of the industry's potential for growth and profitability.

The industry's evolution and increasing investment trends will play a critical role in supporting global economic growth, creating jobs, and fostering innovation in the logistics and supply chain. The problems are highlighted in the investment of the supply chain. That is lacking the coordination in partnership between private as well as state business, incomplete information about the features of investment projects, as well as underdeveloped methodology investment creates underestimation of projects.

Keywords: supply chain, logistics, investment, and innovation process, global market.

Introduction

In the logistics industry the competitiveness of improving the economy through the development of infrastructure in transportation. This industry is an important pillar to promote the national economy. This is an effective way to discuss the crises, trends as well as the strengthening of globalization. This becomes a competitive environment which shows the innovation in logistic technologies. As per infrastructure transportation with an international growth role, over the past years, the imports and exports share of developed country's GDP has increased 2 times its rate [McCloskey D., 2012]. In 2013 and 2016 corporations of logistics increased from 8.6% to 9.9% of the cost of logistics [McCloskey D., 2012]. In the logistics industry, progress and technology changes the way of economic development and also promote this development as coordination for the regional economy. This promotes the smart logistics industry as the innovation and transportation of logistics. Innovative investment in logistics is very important. Because the conditions and financing for transportation and maintenance infrastructure improve their efficiency. The research object is supply chain development and the subject is the importance and the role of investments in supply chain development. It's important to examine the problems as well as the roles of process in investment for supply chain development. In the supply chain development private, local as well as state authorities operate in transportation whereas the logistics industry used to in hands investment.

D. McCloskey used the method called rhetorical which explains the new stages of life in the market test and improvement in the supply chain. According to his idea whereas an analysis of investment shows the fundamental concept and the innovation process of the economy which makes the initial impulse of economic growth. This idea is an understanding of innovative social values in the industry, supply chains, and their services. This gives the result of fundamental provisions process of investing in innovation and that can be extended to the sphere of technologies in logistics. There is a lack of investment in infrastructure transportation which is the main cause of inefficiency in the supply chain. Many of the studies done recently show that logistics have great potential for development. Both on a scale of macro and micro economy. Companies work traditionally to coordinate with the global supply chain in which they build a complex set of relationships that affect significantly the distribution of economic benefits in the development of the supply chain as well as in the consequences of it in the long term. Investing in the supply chain development allows the expansion of infrastructure, using transportation of new types as well as making units for transportation and creating and managing logistics and information over long distances. The minimizing of cost in logistics and transport is achieved only by giving the introduction of logistic technologies, this makes it economically viable in the supply chain as well as creates additional profits for all the employees in the network of logistics. Therefore, investment in supply chain development, as well as infrastructure, gives significant and positive results for the people participating in the industry of transport and logistics.

The industry's evolution and increasing investment trends will play a critical role in supporting global economic growth, creating jobs, and fostering innovation in the logistics and supply chain. The Processing of data, as well as information in the field of technology advancement, contributed to the logistics development and this reduced its transportation cost and its cost. However, the implementation actively is information technologies are the main advantage in the development of logistics. This gives processing of data in a large amount as well as the use of information and analytical

centers of logistic provides¹. Investment in the supply chain gives economic benefits as well as development for countries. In the transport sector efficiency was increased from 10% later on it will be increased by 0.8% (Dmitriyev A.V., 2017). In the transport industry, the public sector improves profitability, and efficiency, as well as increases investment infrastructure of the business sector, and this gives carriages to invest in private capital (Aschauer D.A., 1989a, b; Banister D., Berechman J., 2000). From 2000 to 2010 China decided to invest in transport infrastructure and there was an increase annually of 15% to 18% which shows the growth in the economy by 8% [Ansar A., Flyvbjerg B., Budzier A., et al., 2016]². The investment in the infrastructure gives a reduction in transportation costs as well as company operating expenses. This positively and directly affects the development of the whole supply chain. As per economic theory investment and infrastructure considers reasonable technology investments aimed at cost reduction. This infrastructure investment research shows the result in projects infrastructure which means that it requires assessment in detail with a specific project and this demands management who are qualified [Flyvbjerg B., Bruzelius N., Rothengatter W., 2003; Flyvbjerg B., Garbuio M., Lovallo D., 2009; Rogoff W., Reinhart C., 2010; Flyvbjerg B., Holm MKS, Buhl SL, 2005]. Investing in the state-level supply chain means estimation in investment decisions concerning transport infrastructure, that is an investment with a profit of 100\$ million and the investment framework definition which means infrastructure as well as transport companies.

The logistics industry as well as objects of individual transport were the main scope of investing in the supply chain. The investment into the development of the infrastructure will make it possible for logistic companies to use the new roads of transport as well as modernize the processes in logistics and reduce the cost as well as improve the quality of the supply chain. This decision of investing in the logistics

¹ Statistics ([s.a.]) // United Nations ESCAP. URL: <http://www.unescap.org/our-work/statistics>.

² Statistics database ([s.a.]) // World Trade Organization. URL: <http://stat.wto.org/Home/WSDBHome.aspx?Language=>

industry, as well as transport, affects the value-added structure in the supply chain globally [Blahman L.S., Zyabrikov V.V., 2015; A.Dmitriev, 2007].

Methodology

The methods used in research are statistical analysis, scientific analysis, generalization, graphical as well as the method used by D.McCloskey was rhetorically defined as capitalism which means transition stages to a new way of life which is called supplies improvement and market test [MsCloskey D., 2012]. According to the index of participation in 2000 and 2019 in the global supply chain observed that a lot of countries were more relying on international trade development with the creation of the global supply chain (Fig. 1).

Countries Index World Participation in the Global Supply Chain in 2000 and 2019.

Fig.1. World participation index in the global supply chain.

Interpretation: The figure shows about world participation index in the global chain for the years 2000 and 2019. Countries like China, Germany, the Republic of Korea, Viet Nam and the Russian Federation have significantly increased their participation rate in 2019 in the development and the creation of a global supply chain whereas Malta had an increased participation rate in 2000 but decreased in 2019 which shows the lowest rate of total infrastructure spending. The figure also shows that with

an increase in the investment and transport industry, more companies are participating in the supply chain globally.

Investments structure in the development of logistics and transport at the beginning of 2020.

Fig.2. Investment structure of the logistic industry and transport

Interpretation: The figure shows about insight into the investment structure for logistics and transport development in four countries at the beginning of 2020. The percentages represent the proportion of investment allocated to four categories: human capital development, road infrastructure facilities, information technologies, and transport facilities. The figure shows the largest proportion of investment in the Russian Federation (34%), USA (32%), China (31%), and Germany (27%) allocated to transport facilities. This suggests that Russia also focused on physical infrastructure for transport and placed a higher emphasis on investment in road infrastructure facilities. Similarly, the largest proportion of investment was allocated to road infrastructure facilities of China (33%), the Russian Federation (31%), Germany (28%), and the USA (25%). In comparison to Information Technology and human capital technology the largest proportion of investment was in the USA (28% and 15%), for Germany and China (26%) each and (19% and 10%) whereas for the Russian Federation information technology and development of human capital (10%). The figure shows about Germany placed a higher priority on investment in human capital development, such as education and training, to support the logistics and transport sector. Whereas, China prioritized investment in physical infrastructure for transport,

particularly road infrastructure facilities. that each country had its priorities and strategies for investing in the logistics and transport sector, reflecting differences in their economic development, infrastructure needs, and policy priorities.

Dynamic innovations of investment in the field of supply chain management and logistic industries. (Billion dollars)

Fig.3. Development of management technologies and information systems.

Interpretation: The figure shows the investment trends in the supply chain management and logistics industries worldwide, spanning from 2015 to 2020. This represents the total investment amount in billions of dollars for each year. The data reveals that there has been a positive growth trend in investments in the supply chain management and logistics industries from 2015 to 2020. The total investment in 2015 and 2016 rose to 2501 and to 4253 billion \$ respectively, which shows a 70% increase in just one year. The trend continued, with the investment amount in 2019 increasing to 2020 is 7164 to 12849 billion \$. This shows an almost 80% increase from 2019. The figure indicates a significant global demand for the logistics and supply chain management industry. This demand is likely driven by an increase in global trade and e-commerce, as well as a growing need for efficient and effective transportation and warehousing services.

Investments in the larger share of the development in the field of information technologies as well as supply chain development will trend globally which means

information system investment, as well as technologies used in supply chain management, are trending and growing.

The trend in the process of the supply chain is because these processes are continuously becoming more dynamic as well as more complex within the supply chain national as well as global. The need for logistics and transport gives reliable information technologies which are necessary to control the complete processes in the supply chain. The participants in the supply chain are getting more interested in the introduction of information tools that can provide operations accounting transparency as well as visibility. These information technologies are very popular in Cloud solutions [Valeeva A.N., Semicheva O.S., Valeeva A.N., 2017]. Sharing the information which they allow to receive was shielded throughout in real-time supply chain. The result shows that the control in the degree over the processes of delivery by the owners of the cargo, as well as carriers' competitiveness in the market of logistics, are increased. Cloud technologies, as well as logistic automation, allow for the reduction of cost which is connected with attracting resources for labor, processes in the supply chain, searching for customers and partners, as well as participation in electronic trading. It can also be assumed the investment share in innovative technologies in logistics will increase in the future.

The availability of innovative technologies in the form of the general and specific technical head has a significant impact on supply chain development at the international level. This also contributes to increasing the mobility of the logistics industry. Human capital investment also plays a significant role in supply chain development. So the total investment they have a low share (Fig.3)

In supply chain development, it's important the highlights the common problems. The basic problem is not having proper awareness as well as information from the authorities about the solutions and possibilities. This creates hurdles and obstacles for logistic and transport development. Surmises of cargo are multimodal which shows the features in the development of the infrastructure as this type of service were compared to the passenger traffic development and this is targeted in many countries by the government bodies.

Secondary the problem facing is the evaluating structure and complex procedure in the infrastructure which fully affects the ideas and interests not only of industries and state authorities involved in construction but also of the people of the country. The country's interests are taken into consideration from the positive and significant effect socially in the development of infrastructure as well as the innovative logistic industry.

Measures from the government:

While evaluating projects of investment in the supply chain.

- Environment impact;
- Benefits of security and safety;
- Operating government and cost capital;
- Benefits of carriers and consumers;
- Access to international and national terminals as well as technological transportation usage;
- Industry dynamics and growth in the market.

These are the evaluations of investment projects which would be considered by government officials should supply chains. This investment project has impacts on the environment that is capital expenditure, safety, shippers, and carriers' benefits are taken into consideration mostly. Whereas the development of supply chain benefits, as well as international trade, is often ignored. In that case, implementing the infrastructure benefits in investment projects are bit fully appreciated. An increase in the supply chain makes a positive effect in the analysis using parameters economically about the difference between costs of reduced transport as well as benefits in the supply chain for the nation. The benefit of the development of the supply chain is direct cost reduction, as well as expense saving, they both, depend on product relation as well as the industry in the region. The important result in improving the supply chain efficiency which includes:

- reduction in the cost of logistics;
- should be an increase in the delivery of goods which relates to reducing the working capital cost for all participants in the supply chain;

- should increase in revenues from starting the new model business supply chain as well as the establishment of new business.

To evaluate the various parameters and projects for an assessment of investment in logistics innovative technologies as a participant in the processes of investment in supply chain development. Before deciding on investment following parameters should be taken into consideration.

- the investment scale is taken into account the risk in investment which makes innovative development in the supply chain;

- the cooperation in the area of various parameters for the project and investment should be taken into consideration;

- implementation projects, as well as additional efforts, are required for its successful implementation;

- payback which means long-term and short profit investment in the supply chain.

The problem in the processes of investment in the field of supply chain shows a lack of evolution as well as a methodology for investment projects. The important benefits in the development of the supply chain are jealousy of investment in full assessment as well as the importance of the methods of assessment by agencies of government which are responsive in the decision of investment in the field of logistics and transport industry. Evaluations in projects which need methodological support for economic benefits as well as cost distribution between the local participation international level as well as federal.

Investment in innovative technologies can solve security. Because the transport system and international trade are still important in the turn of security. Participants in the supply chain of any group can control the huge number as well as operations which related to and included in the global supply chain. At the same time companies as well as governments also improve the measures in the related field of the supply chain through corporations.

As a part of the security system in the development of the supply chain, one should take into consideration environmental production (Review, 2017). Many requirements

in the security and safety system in logistics are already in legislation (Federal Law, 1998). For illustration in the period of 2017, Russian railways invested a whole about 5 billion in environmental issues (N. Loginov, 2018). The participants in logistics need to cooperate with suppliers which offer reliable and environmentally friendly solutions (L. Simonova).

The advantage of investment in supply chain and security development should be according to the design which balances the government which increases interest in security in the private sector as well as improving the business processes efficiency within the supply chain. Logistics processes and transport security should comply with rationality principles as well as mention the balance between expenses and income. This approach at the same time also ensures security in the development of a supply chain and allows participation in the international trade system. This can make firms quickly ensure the security of the international supply chain. Therefore the measures in balancing the supply chain security will decrease the chance risk of investors and this will be a reason for increasing investment. Thus, the process of innovation gives the benefit of increasing customers, delivering on time, growing needs, as well as growth in industries. The supply chain development also depends directly on the volume of investment as well as structure. These are variables that largely come to the problems in the logistics industries as well as in their transport. The main focus and directions in the investment development activities are a private-public enhancing partnership, evaluating investment methodology for the development of infrastructure as well as the regulatory framework in the innovative logistics supply chain.

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